

ECONOMICS

CHALLENGES OF GEORGIAN INSURANCE MARKET AND SOLUTIONS TO OVERCOME THEM

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Abstract

The implementation of the principles of inclusive economy in Georgia created a competitive environment in business sector and motivation for successful activity.

Insurance business helps Georgian state to implement active social policies

Agriculture is one of the leading sectors of Georgian economy, therefore development of Agricultural insurance is an important guarantee of social protection and financial stability of farmers in Georgia.

The intensive growth of road traffic in Georgia and the increase in road traffic accidents made the need to create a law in Georgia about "mandatory civil liability insurance of a motor vehicles registered in Georgia". According to this law, third-party road users will be compensated for damage caused by the operation of motor vehicles.

During the "Covid 19" pandemic in Georgia, the form of direct sale of insurance products to corporate and individual clients was introduced in the insurance industry.

Keywords: Inclusive economics, risks, Insurance business, Agricultural insurance, Civil liability insurance.

Implementation of the principles of inclusive economy in Georgia, demanded from Georgian government to increase the targeting of socio-economic policies, which means the effective use of the material, financial and human resources available in the country. The active participation of citizens in industrial relations and the effective use of labor potential should be accompanied by a synergy that ensures the increase in the well-being of the population and the improvement of living conditions.

The main principle of the inclusive economy is establishment of justice mechanisms and tools in the distribution of wealth, which increases the importance of civil sector involvement in economic and public life.

The implementation of the principles of inclusive economy in Georgia created a competitive environment in the business sector and created motivation for successful activity.

Currently, Georgian economic has to deal with two challenges. These are adaptation to the applicable regulations related to joining the European Union and on the other hand protection of the internal market of Georgia.

Social imperatives take an important place in the inclusive economy as a process of socialization of the economy. According to Klaus Schwab, the founder and director of the World Economic Forum, "the existing perception of capital today must be changed. Modern consumers not only want more goods and services for less price, but also expect more social responsibility from corporations. The reset should give everyone who is in the back rows today the right to vote. Some of the pillars of the existing system should be changed, some

should be corrected. This is what is needed for universal progress."¹

Insurance business helps Georgian state to implement active social policies, since it compensates legal and physical persons for the losses caused by the realization of insured risks.

The challenges related to the process of world globalization (Capital concentration in the hands of large corporations, climate changes, pollution of the ecological environment, epidemics and others) have significantly increased the likelihood of risks and the demand for insurance products necessary to protect oneself from these risks.

In 2022, the global insurance business collected more than 5.6 trillion euros in insurance premiums for life, health, property and accident insurance, which is a record compared to previous years and is 4.9% higher than the same rate of the previous year.²

The insurance business of Georgia also grew stably from year to year. "In 2023, the insurance premium collected by insurance companies from direct insurance activities amounted to 1,063.6 million GEL; the similar figure in 2017 was only 441.40 million GEL. According to the results of 2023, the net profit of insurance companies amounted to 73.5 million GEL, while in 2017 their net profit was 20.34 million GEL."³

From year to year, the value of the assets of Georgian insurance companies also increases. In 2023, the total assets of insurance companies amounted to 1300.9 million GEL, and the capital amounted to 374.3 million GEL. While the total amount of assets of insurance companies in 2020 was 915.8 million GEL, and the amount of capital was 279.1 million GEL."⁴

¹ Schwab K., Zahidi S. (2018), 10 Things You - and Your Government - Should Know about Competitiveness in the Fourth Industrial Revolution, [online] 16 October;

² <https://www.interfax.ru/business/904910>

³ <https://insurance.gov.ge/ka/Statistics>

⁴ <https://insurance.gov.ge/ka/Statistics>

Although the insurance industry in Georgia is developing dynamically, its share in the country's economy is still small. "According to the data of 2023, the ratio of the volume of the total insurance premium in relation to the gross domestic product amounted to only -2.0%"⁵, while in the same period the same indicator was 11.6% in the USA, 10.5% in Britain, 5.9% in Germany."⁶

In recent years, new trends in the development of insurance business have appeared in the European insurance market, which is due to new technologies, (including artificial intelligence) demographic changes, and new legislative regulations. Technological innovations have significantly changed the practices of risk assessment, customer relations and database processing in the insurance industry.

The increase in life expectancy in Europe has significantly changed the structure of insurance services, which was reflected in the increase in demand for life and health insurance.

Increased risks from natural disasters due to climate change and meeting their insurance demand have also become one of the significant problems for the European insurance industry.

As for the insurance industry of Georgia, it is characterized by certain specificities and trends, which were formed in the course of the historical development of this branch of the economy since the 1990s. Specificity and trend mean that the leading position in insurance services is occupied by auto insurance and medical insurance. "According to the data of 2023, the share of auto insurance in the total insurance premium was 19.3%, medical insurance - 42.1%."⁷

Agriculture is one of the leading sectors of the Georgian economy, therefore the development of agricultural insurance is an important guarantee of social protection and financial stability of farmers in Georgia. Agricultural insurance not only protects the income of farmers from various risks, but also stimulates the production of agricultural products and increases the export potential of the country. Agricultural insurance has been growing rapidly for the last few years. "In 2023, the amount of premiums raised in this field increased by 112.2% compared to the previous year and amounted to 18.4 million GEL, and according to the data of the nine months of 2024, this number was 21.6 million GEL. We must notice that agricultural insurance is one of the riskiest insurance product. The amount of insurance lose in 2023 amounted to 18.7 million GEL, which means that agricultural insurance was not profitable for the insurance business in 2023."⁸

The agricultural industry in Georgia is significantly affected by natural risks, which are mainly related to climatic conditions. These are: drought, hail, flood and others. Since the production of agricultural products is associated with high costs and risks, it is extremely important to better adjust the state program of agricultural insurance to the needs of farmers and their

financial capabilities in order to increase the interest of farmers in agricultural insurance in Georgia.

The intensive growth of road traffic in Georgia and the increase in road traffic accidents made the need to create a law in Georgia about "mandatory civil liability insurance of a motor vehicles registered in Georgia". According to this law, third-party road users will be compensated for damage caused by the operation of motor vehicles. Only from this line of insurance, business will have an income of approximately 200 million GEL, and insured individuals will be compensated for losses of 120 million per year. "In order to create this effective mechanism of social protection, each vehicle owner is obliged to purchase a compulsory insurance policy and pay insurance premium.

During the "Covid 19" pandemic in Georgia, the form of direct sale of insurance products to corporate and individual clients was introduced in the insurance industry. It is really a convenient form of marketing, because considering the still low purchasing power of the population of Georgia, the value of these products is low and affordable. The ability to obtain insurance services is easy because they are obtained by phone or using the Internet.

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⁷ <https://insurance.gov.ge/ka/Statistics>

⁸ <https://insurance.gov.ge/ka/Statistics>

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